

Deliverable 2.1: Short-term staff exchanges of senior scientists

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Basic information

Project title	Strategies to strengthen scientific excellence and innovation capacity for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal cancers
Project acronym	VISION
Call	H2020-WIDESPREAD-2018-2020
Topic	WIDESPREAD-03-2018
Project type	Coordination and Supporting Action (CSA)
Grant Agreement No.	857381
Nature	R (Document, report - excluding the periodic and final reports)
Dissemination level	PU (Public, fully open, e.g. web)

Executive summary

Within VISION project short-term staff exchanges of senior scientists and Principal investigators (PI) of up to 5 days from the different multidisciplinary teams participating in the project's consortium were planned. These exchanges are expected to promote and strengthen collaborations in the field of GI cancer and application of smart nanomaterials into biomedicine so that the diagnosis and treatment of cancer, including the biosafety of these nanomaterials at bilateral level will be improved. During these visits, specific topics can be discussed and it will provide an opportunity for the different PIs to visit the facilities of all consortium members in order to brainstorm, create and develop ideas for new research projects and strategies.

1 Description of work & main achievements

Senior scientists from other groups of the consortium are expected to visit different laboratories over the course of the project in order to strengthen alliances and collaborations at the European level. Partners have had several discussions regarding this issue during the project meetings - teleconferences as well as during the project Kick-off meeting in November 2019 at BMC SAV. Tentative plans have been made for visits for different researchers. However, their implementation was postponed due to the COVID crisis.

Nevertheless, despite the complicated situation, partners are collaborating virtually (via e-mail communication or teleconferences) and the following outcomes have been achieved:

- SERMAS has extended an invitation to Agapi Kataki (NKUA) and Silvia Pastorekova (director of BMC SAS) for a short-term visit of SERMAS research facilities.
- Two publications were published as open access:
Ciernikova S, Earl J, García Bermejo ML, Stevurkova V, Carrato A, Smolkova B. Epigenetic Landscape in Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma: On the Way to Overcoming Drug Resistance? *Int J Mol Sci.* 2020 Jun 8;21(11):409
Yvonne Kohl, Elise Rundén-Pran, Espen Mariussen, Michelle Hesler, Naouale El Yamani, Eleonora Marta Longhin and Maria Dusinska. Genotoxicity of Nanomaterials: Advanced In Vitro Models and High Throughput Methods for Human Hazard Assessment—A Review. *Nanomaterials* 2020, 10, 1911; doi:10.3390/nano10101911
- One publication was submitted for publication:
Yvonne Kohl, Margit Biehl, Sarah Spring, Michelle Hesler, Vladimir Ogourtsov, Miomir Todorovic, Joshua Owen, Elisabeth Elje, Kristina Kopecka, Oscar Hernando Moriones, Neus G. Bastús, Peter Simon, Tibor Dubaj, Elise Rundén-Pran, Victor Puentes, Nicola William, Hagen von Briesen, Sylvia Wagner, Nik Kapur, Espen Mariussen, Andrew Nelson, Alena Gabelova, Maria Dusinska, Thomas Velten, Thorsten Knoll: Microfluidic in vitro platform for (nano)safety and (nano)drug efficiency screening, *Small*, Special Issue (invited contribution).
- Two H2020 projects were submitted:
 - ARCHIMEDES (Call: H2020-NMBP-TR-IND-2018-2020, 16 partners including NILU, BMC SAV and FhG)
 - AFFECTS (Call: H2020-SC1-BHC-2018-2020, 37 partners including NILU, FhG and BMC SAV)

2 Deviation from the workplan

Due to coronavirus pandemic no exchanges could be realized because it was impossible to travel. Project partners will discuss the plan for the next periods at the regular VISION meetings.

3 Conclusion

We hope that the current COVID crisis situation changes in 2021 and that we will be able to carry out the planned visits of senior scientists. In the mean time, consortium members will continue to have regular teleconferences, thus promoting a constant contact among the PIs and senior members and reinforcing our collaboration interests.